

Welcome to the 5th volume of the EU-HIP Newsletter!

Hello, and welcome to the fifth edition of our Newsletter. This volume will focus on one country - Lithuania. We will shed light on the current state and IT infrastructure present by bringing key insights from the country-specific report. In addition to that, we will present to you the federated automated surveillance in the Netherlands and introduce you to the EU FAB programme.
Let's start exploring!

The EU-HIP consortium is putting great efforts in order to map and understand country-specific IT infrastructures gathering information of high importance in case that a cross-border health threat emerges. Our teams from Sciensano (Belgium) and THL (Finland) have visited Lithuania and with the help of the Lithuanian Health Emergency Situation Centre of the Ministry of Health conducted numerous semi-structured interviews with key stakeholders.

**Getting deeper insight:
meet Lithuania!**

Several institutions in Lithuania are responsible for management of health crises, including:

- Ministry of Health - formulates and implements national health policies, coordinates resources and provides guidelines
- National Public Health Center (NPHC) - protects public health by managing risks related to infectious diseases, environmental factors, services and products provided to consumers
- State Veterinary and Food Safety Service (VMVT) - OneHealth activities; carries out state food and veterinary control, supervision and control of breeding of farm animals and is responsible for veterinary pharmacy
- National Public Health Surveillance Laboratory (NPHSL) - responsible for AMR, biological threats and highly infectious pathogen testing
- Health Emergency Situations Center (HESC) - ensuring the readiness of the healthcare system for emergency situations
- National Crisis Management Centre (NCMC) - includes a situation center that operates 24/7, continuously monitoring threats to national security
- Institute of Hygiene (IH) - monitors the health status of Lithuanian residents and the activities of healthcare institutions, assessing public health inequalities and public healthcare technologies, researching the effects of the work environment on health, strengthening mental health, health education and disease prevention, and developing the competencies of healthcare and pharmaceutical specialists
- State Data Agency (Statistics Lithuania) - responsible for shaping and implementing state policy in official statistics and data governance under the Ministries of Finance and, Economy and Innovation
- State Enterprise Centre of Registers (SECR) - public entity of limited civil liability incorporated by the Government of the Republic of Lithuania; it hosts more than 60 registries, covering different sectors and providing access for a fee to the data
- State Medicines Control Agency - among other duties, monitors the prescriptions issued and the amount of antibiotics sold
- National Food and Veterinary Risk Assessment Institute - the designated risk assessment institution in Lithuania providing scientific and technical assistance in the field of food safety and veterinary, as well performing functions of the national reference laboratory and carrying out laboratory tests in the areas of food and feed safety, quality and animal health

Lithuanian Open Data Portal

The Lithuanian Open Data Portal serves as a unified access point to datasets published by various Lithuanian public sector organizations. It offers technological tools to facilitate the publication and reuse of open data, aiming to enhance transparency, innovation, and public engagement. Datasets are categorized, downloadable in machine-readable formats like CSV and JSON and already visualized with geospatial and temporal facts. A special part is the COVID-19 Portal. It provides COVID-19 dashboards and statistical data related to the pandemic in Lithuania. It offers comprehensive visualizations and up-to-date information on infection rates, testing, vaccinations and other key metrics. The dashboards help track the impact of COVID-19 across different regions of Lithuania, aiding both policymakers and the public in understanding and responding to the health crisis effectively. The data to the COVID-19 dashboard flows directly from the eHealth system. You can reach open both portals using the following links:

Open Data Portal

COVID-19 Portal

The Radiation Protection Center (RPC) is the regulatory authority for radiation protection, responsible for implementing regulatory control over public and environmental exposure, as well as the use of sources of ionizing radiation - except for practices within the nuclear energy field. It also participates in the formulation of the state policy on radiation protection, as entrusted by the Minister of Health, and is responsible for early warning, assessing radiation risks and providing recommendations on protective measures to minimize exposure to radiation. It plays a crucial role in assessing the extent of contamination and informing the public and first responders about potential health risks.

RPC manages the Radiation Early Warning System (RADIS) in Lithuania, overseeing a network of portal monitors across the country. Responsibility for maintenance and receipt of initial notifications in case of any incidents lies with the Center. There are 44 RADIS stations throughout Lithuania, with a higher concentration near the Belarus NPP and the Belarus border, in readiness for potential events in that area. Additionally, four stations are situated in Neris and Nemunas rivers. Data from these RADIS stations are automatically collected and transmitted to the Center's servers every ten minutes. If elevated radiation levels are detected, the team assesses the threat and provides recommendations accordingly.

Validation and verification of the data occur before making it available to the public to avoid unnecessary concern caused by false alarms or technical errors at the monitoring stations. Quality data checks are primarily conducted automatically, except when alarm levels are triggered. In such cases, specialists manually review the data to determine if the alarm is genuine or due to an error. They then make decisions regarding whether the alarm is false or valid, and whether additional measurements or actions are necessary to confirm its accuracy.

Real-time data is available to the public through the RADIS Portal at the following link:

RADIS Portal

Conclusions

Open and interoperable data

Looking at the existing state, Lithuania shows a high level of respecting the FAIR principles in data management. Most of the public sector data is freely available via the Data Portal. If the data is outside the scope of this source, additional datasets and information are available through other parties - for example data on antimicrobial resistance. Interoperability with other Member States and ATHINA depends on the efforts put by all sides involved and thus it is important to reach consensus on common data models to be used.

This overview was designed to introduce you to the most important and interesting topics. If you want to get a complete picture of existing infrastructure in Lithuania, including legislation and more complex technical and operational procedures, we highly recommend you to read the complete Country visit report available on EU-HIP Zenodo:

[Full Report](#)

Netherlands

RIVM (Rijksinstituut Voor Volksgezondheid en Milieu), the National Institute for Public Health and the Environment is pushing the implementation of federated automated surveillance in the Netherlands. While most surveillance structures rely on centralized data collection and storage, the federated model enables the data to be stored locally by data holders (hospitals, primary care units, nursing homes and others). The central surveillance platform collects only the results of already run analyses.

Federated automated surveillance

This way of performing surveillance activities shows multiple advantages compared to centralized services, especially concerning data ownership and GDPR. In addition, it requires less operational capacities in most cases and is easily scalable to include more data holders in future analyses making it more agile in case of an emerging health crisis.

EU FAB

The EU FAB programme is an initiative by the European Commission aimed at establishing a network of 'ever-warm' manufacturing capacities for vaccines and therapeutics within the European Union. This network is designed to be operational at all times, ensuring that production capabilities can be rapidly activated in response to public health emergencies.

The primary objective of EU FAB is to maintain sufficient and agile manufacturing capacities for various vaccine types, including mRNA-based, vector-based, and protein-based vaccines. By reserving these capacities, the EU aims to ensure quick and equitable access to vaccines and therapeutics during health crises, thereby enhancing the overall preparedness and resilience of its healthcare systems.

Learn more about EU FAB with the provided resources

[EU FAB Factsheet](#)

[EU FAB from the news](#)